

TECHNISCHE
UNIVERSITÄT
WIEN

Institut für
Computertechnik
Institute of
Computer Technology

Bachelor's Thesis

submitted by

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Power Profiling of Machine Learning Accelerators using MLPerf

In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of

Bachelor of Science (BSc)

Study code: 033 235

Field of study: Electrical Engineering and Information Technology

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Vienna, Austria, 21 February 2022

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```
@Thesis{Alge2022,  
  type    = {Bachelor's Thesis},  
  author  = {Nikolas Alge},  
  title   = {{Power Profiling of Machine Learning Accelerators using MLPerf}},  
  school  = {Vienna University of Technology (TU Wien)},  
  year    = {2022},  
  address = {Gusshausstrasse 27--29 / 384, 1040 Wien},  
  month   = {February},  
}
```

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Acknowledgements

Above all, I would like to thank my supervisor Christian Krieg. Besides giving me the opportunity to work on this project, he provided essential feedback and motivation during the whole process of creating this thesis.

Moreover I wish to express my sincere thanks to Matthias Wess for the many hints he gave me whenever a problem occurred as well as letting me be part of a paper. He also generously allowed me to use some of the data here.

I would like to thank Matvey Ivanov for the guidance regarding the measurement setup and his software, which made measurements work like a charm.

Furthermore I want to express my gratitude to Leandro Libutti for taking his time to answer my questions regarding his paper.

Abstract

There exists a vast amount of possibilities of hardware platforms and models when implementing a machine learning problem. In order to be able to choose the best approach, an estimator of important parameters like latency, power consumption and accuracy would be beneficial. To build such a tool, it is necessary to characterize hardware and models first. This is done in this work by reproducing the results of a study that examines the Google Coral USB Accelerator and the Intel Neural Compute Stick 2. Especially, the power consumption is looked at in more detail by using a sampling rate of 100kS/s. The findings include power profiles of the mentioned hardware accelerators executing MobileNetV1 and Inception V1 by means of the MLPerf Inference benchmark. Additionally, the accuracy and latency are examined and the results are compared to the related study. Moreover, a measurement setup, including a USB dongle for simple and reliable data acquisition, is presented. A sampling rate of 500kS/s allows it to evaluate each individual layer of a model regarding power and latency during inference. The presented work serves as a basis for further investigations in the field of parameter estimation.

Kurzfassung

Soll ein Machine Learning Problem implementiert werden, stehen eine beachtliche Anzahl an Hardware Plattformen und Modellen zur Verfügung. Um die effizienteste Lösung zu einem Problem zu finden, wäre es hilfreich, wenn spezifische Parameter einer Inferenz abgeschätzt werden können. Diese Größen sind die Latenz, die Genauigkeit, der Energieverbrauch sowie die maximale Leistungsaufnahme. Um solch eine Abschätzung durchführen zu können, müssen Plattformen und Modelle in einem ersten Schritt charakterisiert werden. Dies wurde in dieser Arbeit durch die Reproduktion eines Papers, in dem der Google Coral USB Accelerator und der Intel Neural Compute Stick 2 untersucht werden, durchgeführt. Besonderer Fokus wird auf die Leistungsaufnahme gelegt, die mit Hilfe eines Messgeräts mit 100kS/s aufgezeichnet wird. Mit Hilfe des MLPerf Inference Benchmark werden Inferenzen von MobileNetV1 und Inception V1 auf den Beschleunigern ausgeführt und deren Leistungsprofile gemessen und analysiert. Zusätzlich werden die Genauigkeit und Latenzen betrachtet und die Resultate mit denen des Papers gegenübergestellt. Außerdem wird eine Messschaltung mit USB Adapter zur zuverlässigen Messung der Daten vorgestellt. Eine noch höhere Abtastrate von 500kS/s erlaubt es zusätzlich einzelne Layer eines Modells zu analysieren. Die präsentierten Ergebnisse dienen als Grundlage für weitere Untersuchungen im Bereich der Abschätzung zentraler Parameter einer Inferenz.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

There exists a large variety of combinations of software and hardware that can be used to execute machine learning (ML) algorithms. To utilize the most efficient way, a prediction of inference parameters, like energy consumption or latency, would be beneficial. This thesis is part of a larger research project, whose central point is the estimation of these parameters. We particularly focus on so-called hardware accelerators to perform ML inferences.

These accelerators are specifically designed to run machine learning operations. Since the latency of an inference lies in the range of a few milliseconds, the sampling rate needs to be adequately high. As it is not certain that the manufacturer of an accelerator provides APIs for profiling, they have to be treated like a black box.

The goals of this thesis include to better understand the process of inference as a whole and to examine the differences between hardware and software combinations. Beyond that, characterization parameters should be determined. This is done by measuring the power draw of the hardware. So the question is raised: What information can you gather about the behavior of these accelerators by looking at the power profile? In the paper of Libutti *et al.* [10], a benchmarking suite is applied on two accelerators and two machine learning models and their power draw is measured. This thesis replicates these measurements and expands on them.

State of the Art presents the methodology and results of [10] as well as the contributions of this thesis. In *Methodology*, the theoretical background and the methodical approach are discussed. *Evaluation* shows the setup and the results. We investigate how we can realize a measurement environment to produce reliable data (Section 4.1.1) and look into an implementation of MLPerf (Section 4.1.2).

Given this setup, we want to:

- Look at the inference process at a whole to better understand the power needs of the different parts (Section 4.2.1).
- Replicate the results of the related study and compare the findings (Section 4.2.2).
- Look at a single inference and analyze parameters of each layer of a model (Section 4.2.4).

Finally, the results are discussed.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

In this chapter the related work is presented. Furthermore, the limits of this approach are analyzed and conclusions are drawn on how we can built upon these ideas.

2.1 Related Work

In “Benchmarking Performance and Power of USB Accelerators for Inference with MLPerf” [10], Libutti et al. use MLPerf to examine the two USB ML accelerators Google Coral USB Accelerator (Coral) and the Intel Neural Compute Stick 2 (NCS2). The tests are executed for an image classification problem. For this application MLPerf supports ImageNet [13] with MobileNetV1 [6]. Additionally, Inception V1 [15] was chosen as a more computation heavy alternative. In order to examine the behavior of the ML system given a specific number of samples at specific time intervals, the MultiStream Mode of MLPerf is used, as it provides exactly that. The number of samples in a query are used as a parameter for most measurements. The power measurement is obtained by using a 0.1Ω shunt in combination with INA219 and an Digispark I2C-Tiny-USB device for the communication to a PC. A measurement is taken each $0.532ms$, 32 values are averaged and then recorded. This results in an sampling frequency of $1.88kS/s$, but the averaged values arrive at a rate of $58.8S/s$. That equals to a sample every $0.532ms$, the averaged values arrive every $17.02ms$. In addition to the shunt voltage, the bus voltage was also obtained and included in the calculation of the power.

The measurements consist of these graphs:

- Latency per image over query size
- Power over query size
- TOPS/W over query size
- Accuracy in relation to TOPS and TOPS/W

The findings show the 1.5-7 times lower inference latency for Coral. Furthermore, Coral also exhibits lower maximum power draw and therefore higher energy efficiency. These benefits come in the cost of prediction accuracy, as the inference on Coral results in around 3% lower values for both models. According to the paper, this is caused by the lower precision number format used with the Coral device (INT8 vs. FLOAT16 on NCS2).

2.2 Contributions

In this work we want to replicate the results gathered in Libutti *et al.* [10] and expand on them.

One of the limitations of this article lies in the sampling rate. Due to the very short inference duration of Coral ($\approx 3ms$), there are only around six samples taken for a single inference. This thesis aims at analyzing the presented black box in more detail. This is achieved by using a higher sampling frequency of $100kS/s$ at least. Therefore a sample is returned every $10\mu s$, resulting in a minimum of 300 samples per inference.

Additionally, this thesis documents the hardware and software setup in much more detail. As for the fact that the setup preparation can be time consuming in itself, it provides a solid foundation for future investigations in this area.

The contributions of this thesis are:

1. A methodology to automatically perform power measurements on ML accelerators
2. Documents to reproduce a plug-in dongle for easily setting up the measurement environment
3. An in-depth look at the MLPerf benchmarking suite and its reference implementation
4. An evaluation of accelerator power profiles
5. A comparison to a similar study conducted by Libutti *et al.* [10], with a much higher sampling rate and therefore more accurate results
6. A methodology and analysis of single layer latency and power as seen in Wess *et al.* [16], to which I contributed to

Chapter 3

Methodology

This chapter covers the theoretical background as well as the methodical approach applied in this thesis.

3.1 Theoretical Background

In this section, the basic terms of machine learning are discussed. Other topics, like accelerators, power estimation and the MLPerf Inference benchmark are also explained briefly.

3.1.1 Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning

Artificial intelligence (AI) tries to create machines that mimic the intelligence of living beings. Since the exact meaning of intelligence is not clearly defined, an exact answer of what counts as AI is also pretty challenging. Despite that, this term is widely used in the field.

Machine learning (ML) is a part of AI and uses statistical methods to gather knowledge. “It enables computers to find intuitive information by using algorithms that repeatedly learn from data instead of being explicitly programmed about where exactly to look for a piece of information” [11]. There are three types of ML algorithms: Supervised, unsupervised and reinforcement learning. When using supervised learning, the ML System learns by looking at labeled example data (training) and later applies the gathered knowledge to new data (inference).

A **machine learning model** is a file that stores the algorithm and data that is used to execute an inference. It can be trained and then represents the gathered knowledge. The models used in this thesis were already trained by supervised learning.

An **artificial neural network (ANN)** is a type of model that consists of connected nodes. Based on the position of the nodes in the network, they are assigned to layers. There is the input layer, which takes the input data, the output layer, which represents the output data and the hidden layer(s) between in- and output. The knowledge they hold is represented non-symbolic. This means, that the information is stored implicitly in the model and any insights regarding the specific approach taken for each data sample can therefore not be gained. If a lot of hidden layers are used, the term Deep Learning (DL) is used.

3.1.2 Machine Learning Accelerators

To calculate the output of an ANN, a vast amount of matrix multiplications have to be performed. While GPUs and FPGAs can perform much better than CPUs when executing these operations, they are still not optimized for these tasks. Therefore, special ASICs are designed, so that the inference can be carried out faster and with lower energy consumption. These are called machine learning accelerators and products for different applications are already designed and distributed by a lot of companies. Examples include the Cloud TPU by Google used in Servers for Cloud AI Applications since 2016 and Apple's Neural Engine incorporated in the A11 from 2017.

To perform inference at the edge, low-power solutions are provided. They come in different form factors, for examples as USB accelerators. Two of them are examined in this thesis.

Google Coral USB Accelerator

The Google Coral USB Accelerator (Coral) [5] inherits the Edge TPU ASIC, which was initially introduced in 2018. It is capable of performing 4 trillion (fixed-point) operations per second ($4TOPS$). As a machine learning framework *TensorFlow lite* is used. Coral supports two operation modes. With standard frequency it runs at $250MHz$, in maximum frequency mode at $500MHz$.

Intel Neural Compute Stick 2

The Intel Neural Compute Stick 2 (NCS2) [9] is powered by a Intel® Movidius™ Myriad™ X Vision Processing Unit (VPU) and was introduced in 2018. It uses the Intel Distribution of the *OpenVINO™ toolkit*. It supports two different operation modes, synchronous and asynchronous. When using synchronous mode inferences are executed successively, while asynchronous mode enables parallel execution. In this thesis only synchronous mode is utilized.

3.1.3 Power Estimation

There is a vast amount of options an engineer is confronted with when deciding how a specific ML problem should be implemented. This refers to the framework, model, data set, graph formats, hardware targets and so on. To find the combination most suitable for the specific problem, it would be helpful if certain parameters of an inference execution could be estimated beforehand given the different scenarios.

When evaluating the quality of ML inferences, the latency and accuracy are important factors. Due to the power constraints of machine learning at the edge two additional parameters are paramount. This leads us to the four parameters:

- Latency
- Accuracy
- Maximum power draw
- Energy consumption

In this thesis we specifically pay closer attention to the power and energy aspects.

As a first step models and hardware targets should be characterized with certain values. For a model, this could be the total number of operations, for a specific hardware target its energy usage per operation.

3.1.4 MLPerf Benchmark

MLPerf benchmarks are part of the MLCommons consortium [1].

MLCommons

MLCommons is a non-profit, open engineering consortium founded in 2020 by over 50 supporting organizations of different backgrounds and sizes in the ML field. MLCommons aspires to push machine learning innovation and create positive impacts on society as a result. In order to accomplish this goal three main pillars were defined by MLCommons [1]:

- Create useful measures of quality and performance of ML systems
- Create large scale open datasets
- Create common development practices and resources

The first aforementioned point is provided by means of the MLPerf benchmarks.

MLPerf are machine learning benchmarking suites developed since 2018. They can be divided into MLPerf Training, with its first version releasing in May 2018, and MLPerf Inference, initially releasing in June 2019. Additionally, dedicated versions of the benchmarks are in development for specific applications, for example “Training: HPC” (High Performance Computing), “Inference: Tiny” for ultra-low-power ML on embedded devices and “Inference: Mobile” for Notebooks and Smartphones.

MLPerf Inference Benchmark

The following sections were excerpted from Reddi *et al.* [12].

Due to the great amount of different possibilities of ML inference implementations, benchmarking of ML systems is a challenging task. The MLPerf Inference benchmark, “MLPerf”, accomplishes this by providing a benchmark, that is “architecturally neutral, representative, and reproducible”.

To run inferences, a so-called *Inference Submission System* is required. It consists of a System under Test (SUT), the Load Generator (LoadGen) and a Dataset. The LoadGen is provided, the dataset to use is specified by MLPerf. The SUT is provided as a reference implementation. MLPerf is defined as a semantic-level benchmark. This means that the task and rules are specified by MLCommons, but the specific implementation is left to the user. Despite that fact, a reference implementation is provided in Python for each of the supported areas of ML benchmarking, e.g. vision or speech recognition. It can already be used to test certain scenarios and is located in the respective folder for each application.

MLPerf Reference Implementation - SUT

As mentioned in the last section, the specific implementation of the benchmark lies with the user (even though there is a reference implementation provided). The SUT has to follow determined rules that define the allowed and prohibited techniques:

Allowed techniques are:

- Arbitrary data arrangement
- Different input and in-memory representations of weights
- Mathematically equivalent transformations and approximations
- Out-of-order query processing
- Replacing dense operations with mathematically equivalent sparse operations
- Fusing and unfusing operations
- Dynamically switching between one or more batch sizes
- Untimed preprocessing
- Quantization and calibration

Prohibited is:

- Retraining and pruning
- Caching
- Optimizations that are benchmark or dataset aware

The reference implementation provides the functionality for preprocessing, the execution of inferences and the post processing of the results. It is looked at in more detail in [Section 4.1.2](#).

LoadGen

The tasks of the Load Generator are to generate the traffic and to measure the performance. There are four different Test Modes which are described in [Table 3.1](#).

Table 3.1: LoadGen Test Mode

Test Mode	Description
AccuracyOnly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Runs each sample from the dataset at least once • Accuracy results are output to <code>mlperf_log_accuracy.json</code>, which can be processed with a provided accuracy script and are processed via the reference implementation and output to <code>results.json</code> • Sample size can be limited by count parameter; this is not MLPerf compliant
PerformanceOnly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Runs the performance traffic for a given TestScenario (test scenarios see Table 3.2) • Uses a fraction of the dataset, but enough to determine the latency values with enough confidence
SubmissionRun	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Runs AccuracyOnly mode followed by PerformanceOnly mode • Both are required to validate MLPerf submissions
FindPeakPerformance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For MultiStream scenario: Detects the maximum samples-per-query • For Server scenario: Detects the maximum queries per second • Not applicable for SingleStream and Offline scenario

There are four Test Scenarios presented in [Table 3.2](#).

Table 3.2: LoadGen Test Scenario

Test Scenario	Description
SingleStream	Queries with one image each are sent sequentially.
MultiStream	Sends N samples every $50ms$ for object detection (N is specified by <code>--samples-per-query</code> parameter). Benchmark result is pass, if a percentile of per query latency is below $50ms$. This mode is used in Libutti <i>et al.</i> [10].
Server	Query arrival is random.
Offline	A single query with all samples is sent.

The results are presented in the output files described in [Table 3.3](#).

Table 3.3: LoadGen Output

Output File	Description
<code>mlperf_log_accuracy.json</code>	Used for AccuracyOnly mode, contains accuracy information. The accuracy can be obtained with the accuracy script included in MLPerf.
<code>mlperf_log_summary.txt</code>	Used for PerformanceOnly mode, contains timing information.
<code>mlperf_log_detail.txt</code>	Contains detailed log of LoadGen processes.
<code>mlperf_log_trace.json</code>	Contains tracing information.

The installation of the LoadGen as well as the generation of the documentation will be explained shortly in [Software Setup](#).

3.2 Methodical Approach

The ultimate goal, to which this thesis contributes to, is to estimate the parameters of an ML inference. The focus here is directed to energy and power. As a first big step a characterization for different hardware and models has to be made so that the behavior can be estimated. For this, we replicate the measurements taken in [10] by using the same hardware accelerators and models. These are the Google Coral USB Accelerator and the Intel Neural Compute Stick 2 in combination with MobileNetV1 and Inception V1.

For the characterization we chose a high level approach. The accelerators are viewed as a black box, we perform inferences and the output is analyzed. The output is the power profile and other parameters like latency and accuracy. The advantage of this approach is that it can be used for very different hardware setups. For Coral, only very few technical specifications are actually disclosed and we can only speculate about the internal structure. Even the provided API doesn't provide many more insights or profiling tools.

To run inferences, the reference implementation of the MLPerf benchmarking suite was chosen. It is used as a foundation, because it already provides a lot of the needed functionality. It is used for preprocessing, to generate queries in different scenarios, report latencies and validate the accuracy. The actual benchmark targets are not examined here.

For the measurement of the power profile we use a quite simple approach by placing a shunt in the USB power line. We then capture the shunt voltage at a high sampling rate of $100kS/s$ in order to be able to see the different parts of the inference process clearly.

As a first step we examine the power profile of the whole inference in order to better understand it and get a sense for the different magnitudes of values in different parts of the process. Then we replicate the article with a higher sampling rate and analyze and compare the results. As a final step, a single inference is observed and analyzed in more detail.

Chapter 4

Evaluation

This chapter covers the experimental setup regarding the hardware and software side. Then, the experimental data gathered by means of the setup and their interpretation is shown.

4.1 Experimental Setup

To run inferences with MLPerf on different accelerators and examine their power profile, a measurement setup was built to ensure measurements can be recorded and evaluated easily. This section is split up into Hardware Setup and Software Setup.

4.1.1 Hardware Setup

In order to examine both accelerators, they are connected to a PC, inferences are executed and their power consumption is observed. The measurement of the power consumption of the accelerator is done by placing a shunt in the power line of a USB 3.2 Gen 1 Cable (i.e. the equal specification as USB 3.0 or USB 3.1 Gen 1), which is used to connect the accelerator to a PC. We then capture the voltage drop across the resistor with a voltmeter. The power consumption then results in (4.1).

$$P_{Accelerator} = \frac{U_{Shunt}}{R_{Shunt}} * (U_{VBUS} - U_{Shunt}) \quad (4.1)$$

with:

- $P_{Accelerator}$ = power consumption of the accelerator
- U_{Shunt} = voltage drop across the shunt
- R_{Shunt} = shunt resistance (0.1Ω)
- U_{VBUS} = USB supply voltage ($5V$)

There were two measurement setups used in this thesis, which will be explained next.

Fig. 4.1: Measurement Setup with DAQ Device USB-201

The first setup (“local”) uses the USB-201 data acquisition (DAQ) device from Measurement Computing, which is 91€ [3]. The measurement setup looks like Fig. 4.1. It is capable of capturing an input voltage with $100kS/s$ at a resolution of $12bit$. If more than one input is connected, a multiplexer is used, so the sampling rate is split between the channels. Since the device is equipped with single-ended inputs only, the voltage has to be measured in relation to GND. First, I tried to measure the voltage on both sides of the shunt in relation to ground and subtract these values in order to get the voltage drop across the shunt. But the therefore lowered sampling rate and the serial acquisition of the voltages result in non meaningful data in this use case. Another possibility would be to place the shunt into the GND line. There is one thing to consider when using this approach: Whenever the USB Cable is connected to an accelerator, three paths of the USB cable are connected electrically. These are the GND (pin 4), GND_DRAIN (pin 7) and the Shield (housing) pins. So all of the three paths need to be interrupted by the shunt. As there arose problems with the modified USB cable, I decided against this method. Instead, I decided to use the INA180A2 Current Sense Amplifier by Texas Instruments for about 1€ [8]. It takes the shunt voltage as the input and outputs a voltage with respect to GND. There are different gain options which have a different bandwidth. For this application, I chose the A2 device with a gain of $50V/V$ and a bandwidth of $210kHz$. To get the setup as reliable as possible, a USB Adapter was created. It is equipped with the shunt and the INA180 on board (Fig. 4.2). Therefore the modification of a USB cable is not necessary anymore.

Fig. 4.2: USB Adapter with INA180 on board

The second setup (“NUC”) is located at the EML Laboratory at TU Wien. It uses an Intel NUC PC as a host with a

connected USB-1608GX data acquisition device from Measurement Computing, which is 605€ [2]. This DAQ device supports 8 differential inputs with a resolution of 16bit and a sampling rate up to 500kS/s . Since it supports differential inputs, the voltage drop across the shunt can be measured directly. Additionally, in this setup, the USB VBUS line is not powered by the host, but by a separate power supply in order to get a stable, well-defined voltage.

4.1.2 Software Setup

Software Environment

The local software environment was set up in a virtual machine on a Windows PC. The host runs *Windows 10 Version 21H1*, the guest runs *Ubuntu 20.04.3 LTS* within *Oracle VM VirtualBox*. For *VirtualBox*, Version 6.1.28 is used with the *Oracle VM VirtualBox Extension Pack* for USB 3 support. Besides Python, specific software is required for each one of the accelerators:

1. Coral supports two frequency modes. For each mode, there is a respective Edge TPU runtime that needs to be installed (*libedgetpu1-std/libedgetpu1-max*). Additionally, the *tflite_runtime* package is required, which contains the TensorFlow Lite interpreter. Alternatively, the full *TensorFlow* package can be installed.
2. The NCS2 requires the *OpenVINO™ Toolkit*.

Both accelerators are added as a USB device to *VirtualBox*, so they are recognized. During inference, both accelerators reconnect as a USB Device with a different product-ID. Therefore these devices need to be added to *VirtualBox* as well.

To use the DAQ devices the package *uldaq* was installed via *pip*. Additionally, I used the *powerutils* package provided by the CDL EML [4].

All software versions are shown in table [Table 4.1](#).

Table 4.1: Software Versions

Oracle VM VirtualBox	6.1.28
Ubuntu	20.04.3 LTS
Python	3.8.10
openvino-ubuntu20	2021.2
tensorflow	2.6.0
tflite-runtime	2.5.0
uldaq	1.2.1
libedgetpu1-std/max	16.0
MLPerf Inference	0.7.1

The *MLPerf Inference* benchmark can be cloned from GitHub (use the `--recurse-submodules` argument). Afterwards the *LoadGen* needs to be installed (explained in the `README_BUILD.md` in `inference/loadgen`). If a documentation of the *LoadGen* is desired, it can be generated with the documentation generator *doxygen*. In order for the benchmark to work with the accelerators, a backend for each one needs to be created. Furthermore new dataset preprocessing methods need to be added to account for the data formats the accelerators use.

MLPerf Reference Implementation - SUT

To get MLPerf to work with the accelerators, modifications need to be made to the reference implementation, located in `vision/classification_and_detection/python`. This section explains the necessary changes and the dataflow of the reference implementation. The document tree looks like this:

```
inference
├── vision/classification_and_detection/python
│   ├── main.py
│   ├── backend_openvino_ncs2.py
│   ├── backend_tflite_coral.py
│   ├── dataset.py
│   └── [...]
```

Table 4.2 shows the functionality of each single file and what changes need to be made.

Table 4.2: SUT Files

File	Description	Changes
<code>main.py</code>	Run the benchmark with this file.	Added new entries to <code>SUPPORTED_DATASETS</code> and <code>SUPPORTED_PROFILES</code>
<code>backend_openvino_ncs2.py</code>	Its main methods provide functionality for the loading of the model and inference execution on the NCS2.	Created this new backend for NCS2 compatibility.
<code>backend_tflite_coral.py</code>	Its main methods provide functionality for the loading of the model and inference execution on Coral.	Created this new backend for Coral compatibility.
<code>dataset.py</code>	Handles the pre- and postprocessing.	Added preprocessing methods for INT8 (Coral) and FLOAT16 (NCS2).

The dataflow of the reference implementation is presented in Fig. 4.3. Now, the input, the process steps and the output are explained in more detail. The **input** parameters can be seen in Table 4.3 and Table 4.4.

Fig. 4.3: MLPerf Dataflow

Table 4.3: SUT Input Parameters

Input	Description	Code Sample
Model	Is the path to the model file.	<code>--model models/mobilenet_v1_1.0_↪224_quant_edgetpu.tflite</code>
Dataset Path	Is the path to the folder containing the dataset and the <code>val_map.txt</code> (see Dataset on how to get the <code>val_map</code>).	<code>--dataset-path dataset/↪ILSVRC2012_img_val</code>
Profile	The profile sets default arguments like the preprocessing and the framework that is used for the run. It is the key of a Python dict.	<code>--profile [mobilenet_coral,↪mobilenet_ncs2]</code>
Maximum Batchsize	Set this parameter to the batch size of the model. Coral only supports a batch size of 1, the NCS2 up to 128 (refers to N in NHWC, you have to hand this parameter to the Model Optimizer when compiling the model).	<code>--max-batchsize [N]</code>

The LoadGen Parameters are also given to `main.py`. The most important ones are shown in [Table 4.4](#).

Table 4.4: LoadGen Input Parameters

Input	Description	Code Sample
Scenario	Sets LoadGen Scenario, as shown in Table 3.2 .	<code>--scenario [SingleStream,↪MultiStream, Server, Offline]</code>
Samples per Query	Only used in MultiStream Mode. Sets number of samples that are sent each query. Set to $\text{max-batchsize} * n$, where n is a positive integer.	<code>--samples-per-query [number of↪samples]</code>
Accuracy-Only Mode	Use LoadGen AccuracyOnly mode instead of PerformanceOnly mode (Table 3.1).	<code>--accuracy</code>
Count	Choose how many samples to use for inference. Not MLPerf compliant for AccuracyOnly mode, use for PerformanceOnly mode or for testing.	<code>--count [number of images to↪use from the dataset]</code>

The benchmark process is split into five steps. Code samples are from `main.py`.

1. **Preprocessing:** The dataset is preprocessed in this step if this was not already done in a previous run. This includes resizing, cropping and the quantization. The preprocessed dataset is stored as `.npy` files.

```
ds = wanted_dataset(data_path=args.dataset_path, [...])
```

2. **Load Model:** Loads the model to the backend given by the profile.

```
model = backend.load(args.model, inputs=args.inputs, outputs=args.outputs)
```

3. **Warmup:** To eliminate latency caused by the preparation of the running environment, five warmup inferences are performed by means of the backend.

```
_ = backend.predict({backend.inputs[0]: img})
```

4. **Create Runner:** A runner object is created. It handles enqueueing, starting of predictions and the post processing. It's methods are used by LoadGen.

```
runner = runner_map[scenario](model, ds, args.threads, post_proc=post_proc, max_
↳batchsize=args.max_batchsize)
```

5. **Run Test with LoadGen:** The LoadGen is started, generates the traffic and creates log files.

```
lg.StartTestWithLogSettings(sut, qsl, settings, log_settings)
```

Results are then **output**. LoadGen log files are explained in [Table 3.3](#). The SUT writes the results to the console and to `results.json`.

The benchmark can be started by executing `python/main.py` with the mentioned arguments, like for example:

```
python python/main.py \
--model ~/models/mobilenet_v1_1.0_224_quant_edgetpu.tflite \
--dataset-path ~/dataset/ILSVRC2012_img_val \
--profile mobilenet_coral \
--max-batchsize 1 \
--scenario MultiStream --samples-per-query 4 \
--accuracy --count 100
```

Model

The models used in this thesis include Inception V1 [15], MobileNetV1 [6] and MobileNetV2 [14].

All models need to be compiled to work with the specific accelerator. The NCS2 and Coral only support models with a static batch size. Coral also only supports a batch size of one in this use case. In the paper by Libutti *et al.* [10], models for NCS2 were used with a batch size up to 128. Greater batch sizes resulted in “NC_OUT_OF_MEMORY” errors. In order to be able to execute tests with query sizes even beyond 128, the batch size for models for the NCS2 was also set to one here.

For the NCS2, the compilation is done with the *Model Optimizer* included in *OpenVINO™*. The model format consists of a `.xml` and a `.bin` file.

For Coral, models can be downloaded directly from their web page. To use *TensorFlow* models, they first have to be converted to 8-bit *TF Lite* models and then have to be compiled with the *Edge TPU Compiler*. Details on the model conversion process can also be found on the Coral page. The model format is `.tflite`.

For *Layer Analysis*, layers should be removed from a Coral model. This is done by utilizing the `--intermediate_tensors` parameter of the *Edge TPU Compiler*. It specifies the output layer for the Edge TPU. The following layers are then not executed on Coral (and are instead run on the CPU). To get the names of the output tensors, visualization tools like *Netron* or the *TF Lite Visualizer* can be used.

Dataset

The dataset, that is applied here, is ImageNet [13]. More specifically, the validation dataset provided for the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge 2012 (ILSVRC2012) is used. It contains 50000 Images with a combined size of 6.7GB. The number of classes each image is assigned to, is 1000. ImageNet is available to download for free for researchers after you sign up. Next, the validation map is needed for the use with MLPerf. It provides the correct class for each image. With it, the accuracy of an inference process can be validated. The README in the MLPerf repository under `inference/vision/classification_and_detection` provides a manual on how to get the `val_map.txt` file by using the *Collective Knowledge* framework (CK).

4.2 Experimental Results

In this part, the experimental results are presented. First, a top-down approach for examining the behavior of ML accelerators is applied. In *MLPerf Inference Power Profile*, the whole power profile of an MLPerf benchmark execution is split into several parts and they are examined regarding latency, power and energy. The second section, *Recreate Measurements*, presents the results of measurements recreated from Libutti *et al.* [10], where the same accelerators are examined and different parameters are analysed. In Section *Power vs. Accuracy vs. Latency*, the power, accuracy and latency are contrasted to each other in a single graph. A bottom-up approach is taken in Wess *et al.* [16], where the each layer of a model is characterized by obtaining its energy consumption and latency. This is shown in the last section, *Layer Analysis*.

All measurements were taken with the MLPerf parameter `max-batchsize` set to one. This parameter specifies the shape of the queries and it has to fit the model batch size, which we specified to be *one* during the compilation.

4.2.1 MLPerf Inference Power Profile

Here, we examine the whole power profile of the two accelerators regarding latency, power and energy consumption in order to better understand how they work and to get a sense for the range of values the parameters lie in.

MLPerf in SingleStream Mode is used to invoke inferences of MobileNetV1. Five warm up inferences followed by four inferences to be examined are executed. The power profile is gathered with the local setup. Additionally, timing information is logged via timers in the code. Since there is no possibility with this setup to synchronize the timers with the measurement device, the timestamps are aligned manually with the inferences. This seems sufficiently accurate,

especially for the means of this part, where primarily average power and energy values as well as time durations are considered.

Table 4.5: Measurement Parameters Power Profile

Measurement Setup	local
Mesured Parameters	power profile, software timestamps
MLPerf Settings	
TestMode	PerformanceOnly
TestScenario	SingleStream
count	4

MLPerf and Model Loading

Fig. 4.4 shows the power profile of the NCS2 with four timestamps. The first two (A+B) are overlapping and represent the start of MLPerf (A) and the start of the “load” method by means of the OpenVINO™ backend (B). The third timestamp (C) depicts the end of the “load” method and the fourth and final one the end of the MLPerf benchmark (D). As we can see, there is some idle minimum power the NCS2 draws while not in use at around $0.65W$. During the loading of the model the power draw is around $1.32W$. After the benchmark is finished the power level returns to the idle state.

Fig. 4.4: Power Profile of the NCS2 executing MobileNetV1

Now the Coral accelerator is examined in standard frequency mode (Fig. 4.5 and Fig. 4.6). The timestamps represent the exact same as in the graph for NCS2, i.e. the first two (very close together) are the start of MLPerf (A) and the start of the loading process (B), the last two represent the end of the load method (C) and the end of MLPerf (D). Two graphs are shown here, they represent the behavior of Coral after a fresh plug-in and an execution of the benchmark after another one was already carried out.

Fig. 4.5: Power Profile of Coral executing MobileNetV1 Initial

Fig. 4.6: Power Profile of Coral executing MobileNetV1 2nd Execution

Two findings can be reported here:

- The loading process, that is the initialization of the interpreter, takes longer after a fresh plug-in.
- The idle power in the initial state is lower compared to after the first benchmark ($0.35W$ compared to $0.98W$). Coral stays at the value of $\approx 1W$ after the benchmark is completed. This behavior can unfortunately not be explained. It is most likely due to a bug, as this was also reported by another user on GitHub.

These points are not true for the NCS2, its power values and loading times are independent of the state its in. As for the fact that in most use cases Coral will not be in its initial state, the power profile after an initialization run is used from here on.

The results are summarized in [Table 4.6](#).

Table 4.6: Results Idle and Model Loading

Hardware	P_{idle} in W	P_{load} in W	t_{load} in s	E_{load} in J
NCS2	0.650	1.321	2.947	3.894
Coral std-f	0.983 (0.351)	0.892	3.610	3.219
Coral max-f	0.984 (0.343)	0.891	3.661	3.264

with:

- P_{idle} = average power during idle (in brackets initial value)
- P_{load} = average power during loading
- t_{load} = loading duration
- E_{load} = energy consumption for loading

Idle power of NCS2 is 66% of the one measured with Coral. If the high idle power of Coral is indeed caused by a bug, the one of the NCS2 is more than 85% higher. The loading of MobileNetV1 is faster on NCS2, but at the cost of a higher

energy consumption. The power profile of Coral in maximum frequency mode is very similar in the part of the model loading, the difference lies in the power draw during inference, which will be explained in the next section.

Inference

Now the inferences are examined with more detail. The power profile of 4 inferences can be seen in Fig. 4.8, Fig. 4.9 and Fig. 4.10 for each hardware (mode). Fig. 4.7 enables a comparison of all three. Numeric results are shown in Table 4.7.

Fig. 4.7: Comparison of the Power Profiles

Fig. 4.8: Power Profile of NCS2 executing MobileNetV1

Fig. 4.9: Power Profile of Coral std-f executing MobileNetV1

Fig. 4.10: Power Profile of Coral max-f executing MobileNetV1

Table 4.7: Results Inference

Hardware	P_{stat} in W	P_{dyn} in W	$t_{predict}$ in ms	E_{inf} in mJ	E_{stat} in mJ	E_{dyn} in mJ
NCS2	1.364	1.804	23.472	42.343	32.016	10.327
Coral std-f	0.988	1.615	3.794	6.127	3.749	2.379
Coral max-f	0.989	1.987	2.427	4.821	2.400	2.421

with:

- P_{stat} = static power usage when ready for inference (model is loaded)
- P_{dyn} = average power of an inference
- $t_{predict}$ = average latency of an inference
- E_{inf} = average energy of an inference
- E_{stat} = static energy during inference
- E_{dyn} = dynamic energy of an inference

Even though the base energy during inference P_{stat} is the same for both Coral modes, the maximum frequency mode has a greater power draw and faster inference, which in result lead to lower energy consumption per inference for maximum frequency mode. The average power draw during inference for the NCS2 lies between the value for the Coral frequency modes. But since the latency is around 6 (10) times larger, the consumed energy is 7 (8.8) times higher than that of Coral running with standard (maximum) frequency.

4.2.2 Recreate Measurements

The objective of this part of the thesis is to reproduce the results of “Benchmarking Performance and Power of USB accelerators for Inference with MLPerf” by Libutti *et al.* [10]. In this article MLPerf was used to examine the two aforementioned accelerators, Coral and NCS2, regarding inference latency, power consumption, efficiency and accuracy. There were two models used: MobileNetV1 and Inception V1.

We examine performance metrics like latency and the MLPerf overhead first, then the power consumption of both hardware accelerators is shown and finally we investigate the energy efficiency and accuracy.

Latency

This experiment shows the mean per-sample latency as reported by MLPerf versus the samples-per-query given to MLPerf as a parameter. This is done for both frequency modes of Coral, the NCS2 and for both models.

When using PerformanceOnly mode of MLPerf in combination with the MultiStream scenario, the count parameter refers to the number of queries. In order to use the same sample count with all measurements, the count (in this case: count of queries) parameter of MLPerf has to be set to $\text{count} = \text{sample-size} / \text{samples-per-query}$. The per-sample latency is output by MLPerf in the `results.json` file as the parameter “mean” and in the `mlperf_log_summary.txt` under “Additional Stats” - “Per-sample latency” - “Mean latency (ns)”.

Table 4.8: Measurement Parameters Latency

Measurement Setup	local
measured	per-sample latency
MLPerf Settings	
TestMode	PerformanceOnly
TestScenario	MultiStream
samples-per-query	[1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64, 128, 256, 512, 1024, 2048]
count	sample-size/samples-per-query

Fig. 4.11: Per-Sample Latency over Samples-per-Query MobileNetV1 (double-logarithmic scale)

Fig. 4.12: Per-Sample Latency over Samples-per-Query Inception V1 (double-logarithmic scale)

In Fig. 4.11 and Fig. 4.12 we can see that the per-sample latency has an approximately linear relation to samples-per-query in double-logarithmic depiction (especially for a query size of greater than 2^4). This equals to exponential behavior with a single-logarithmic x-axis. The “per-sample latency” in this case is the period of time starting with the issue of the query and ends when the inference of the specific sample is complete. Given a batch size of one, all inferences have to be executed in serial order. This results in the matter of fact that for example the inference of the second sample of a query has to be postponed until the first one is completed. Therefore the latency of the second sample of a query will be approximately doubled in comparison to the first one. The third sample will then take around three times as long and so on. All of these per-sample latencies are then averaged. This explains the rise in per-sample latency when the batch size is increased.

When compared to NCS2, the standard frequency mode of Coral results in 15-22% (22-27%) of per-sample latency, the maximum frequency mode in 9-17% (13-22%) for MobileNetV1 (Inception V1).

Now this figure is compared to Fig. 3 in [10], which uses a logarithmic x-axis. The biggest difference is the descending curve in the article, whereas the per-sample latency rises with rising samples-per-query in the graph above. This could be due to the assumption that the paper doesn’t depict the MLPerf reported per-sample latency, but the inference duration.

To compare the graph we use (4.2) to calculate the approximate inference duration.

$$t_{psl} = \sum_{k=1}^{n_{spq}} k * t_{inf} * \frac{1}{n_{spq}} = (1 + n_{spq}) * \frac{n_{spq}}{2} * t_{inf} * \frac{1}{n_{spq}} = (1 + n_{spq}) * \frac{t_{inf}}{2} \implies t_{inf} = \frac{2 * t_{psl}}{1 + n_{spq}} \quad (4.2)$$

with:

- t_{psl} = per-sample latency; is the duration of issue of the query to end of inference averaged over all samples
- t_{inf} = duration of one inference
- n_{spq} = number of samples-per-query

When depicting the inference duration t_{inf} over the n_{spq} , we get Fig. 4.13 and Fig. 4.14. Now the results are similar to the ones in the paper. For NCS2, the latency is greater here. The reason could be the different model batch size used here.

Fig. 4.13: Inference duration over Samples-per-Query MobileNetV1

Fig. 4.14: Inference duration over Samples-per-Query Inception V1

MLPerf Overhead

The measurement in this section is similar to the previous one. Again, the per-sample latency is measured given the samples-per-query. Additionally, we now graph the overhead MLPerf produces. This is done by introducing a software based timer, which returns the time a single inference takes.

Table 4.9: Measurement Parameters Overhead

Measurement Setup	local
measured	per-sample latency, single inference duration
MLPerf Settings	
TestMode	PerformanceOnly
TestScenario	MultiStream
samples-per-query	[1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64, 128, 256, 512, 1024, 2048]
count	sample-size/samples-per-query

In order to compare the duration of one inference to the per-sample latency, we have to take into account that the inferences are executed one after another and the per-sample latency is the duration of the occurrence of a query till the sample is complete. To get the duration of one inference, (4.2) is used again.

To calculate the Error, equation (4.3) is used.

$$e\% = \frac{t_{inf_{MLP}} - t_{inf_{SW}}}{t_{inf_{SW}}} \quad (4.3)$$

with:

- $e\%$ = relative error in %
- $t_{inf_{SW}}$ = duration of one inference as measured with a software based timer
- $t_{inf_{MLP}}$ = duration of one inference as calculated with (4.2), where $t_{psl_{MLP}}$ is reported by MLPerf

Fig. 4.15: Overhead MobileNetV1 Coral std-f

Fig. 4.16: Overhead Inception V1 Coral std-f

Fig. 4.17: Overhead MobileNetV1 Coral max-f

Fig. 4.18: Overhead Inception V1 Coral max-f

Fig. 4.19: Overhead MobileNetV1 NCS2

Fig. 4.20: Overhead Inception V1 NCS2

The results can be seen in Fig. 4.15 - Fig. 4.20. All graphs have in common that the bigger the samples-per-query, the smaller the MLPerf Overhead in %. For maximum frequency mode of Coral, the relative error is much bigger. This can be attributed to the fact that Coral has an inference latency that is only about 20% of that of the NCS2. Therefore the MLPerf Overhead affects the latency much more dramatically. There is quite a bit of deviation from a smooth curve, especially for Coral standard frequency mode and NCS2. This probably originates from random events and could be eliminated by averaging over more measurements.

In Fig. 7 of the article [10], the data for “Time/Image” is the same as in Fig. 3. The basic trajectory and the values of the

graph presented in here are similar. Only speculation can be made on how the measurements were taken in the article. A possibility would be that the calculation presented here was used.

Power Consumption

Now, the power consumption is examined during inference. To measure power, the setup Fig. 4.1 is used. This time, MLPerf is only executed up to a batch size of 32, and therefore there are 32 samples used for all measurements. This is done to keep the measurement duration short. Otherwise the resulting power measurement data files would become too large in size. The mean and maximum power values during a inference are then extracted from the power profile for each inference and are then averaged.

Table 4.10: Measurement Parameters Power

Measurement Setup	local
measured	maximaum and mean power during inference
MLPerf Settings	
TestMode	PerformanceOnly
TestScenario	MultiStream
samples-per-query	[1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32]
count	sample-size/samples-per-query

The idle power was measured after plugging the accelerator into the PC (initial) and after a run of MLPerf was completed (after_inf). Both measurements were taken for 20s, the power values were then averaged.

Table 4.11: Measurement Parameters Idle

Measurement Setup	local
measured	idle after plug in (initial), idle after a MLPerf run (after_inf)
duration	20s

Fig. 4.21: Power Consumption over Samples-per-Query with MobileNetV1 on NCS2

Fig. 4.21 shows that there is no dependence of the power consumption in a inference of the samples-per-query. This is reasonable, since every inference is executed after the other, and is true for every hardware and model combination used here. Therefore we can use the x-Axis to compare the hardware (modes).

Fig. 4.22: Power Consumption MobileNetV1

Fig. 4.23: Power Consumption Inception V1

The first thing to notice is the very similar power consumption when comparing the two models. Inference of inception draws just a little more power. Whereas the idle values are the same for the NCS2 at around $0.65W$, Coral has two different values. After the initial plug-in the power consumption is $0.35W$. When a inference is finished, the power stays at $0.98W$. As already mentioned, this is most likely due to a bug. While the mean and maximum power values for NCS2 and standard frequency mode for Coral are quite similar, for Coral with maximum frequency the maximum power is 149% when compared to standard frequency. The mean power scales with 123%. The maximum power draw of $5W$ is already above the maximum power specification of $4.5W$ of USB 3. An important point to notice is that it could be even higher, as due to the measurement setup only power values up to $5W$ can be measured.

Now the results are compared to Fig. 5 in Libutti *et al.* [10]. In the article, the power depends on the samples-per-query for Coral. This is most likely due to power measurement setup used. It takes a measurement every $0.53ms$ ($1.88kS/s$) and averages 32 values, i.e. an averaged value is given every $17.02ms$. The sampling frequency therefore is $85.8kS/s$. The inference for Coral takes $3.5 - 5ms$. Given the low number of samples-per-query the idle time between queries is included in the measured value and lowers the average. This is probably also the reason why the max power values are much smaller as compared to the measurements taken here. The idle power of the NCS2 is $1.5W$ in [10] compared to $0.65W$ here. The power draw of the NCS2 is $1.5W$ when the model is loaded, this is what is probably measured in the article.

Energy Efficiency

For the energy efficiency of the accelerators, the whole inference process is analyzed regarding its mean power and latency. The power is measured the same way as in [Power Consumption](#). Specifically, the time duration from the end of the warm-up till the end of the last inference is examined.

Table 4.12: Measurement Parameters Efficiency

Measurement Setup	local
measured	mean power during inference, latency
MLPerf Settings	
TestMode	PerformanceOnly
TestScenario	MultiStream
samples-per-query	[1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32]
count	sample-size/samples-per-query

Since the graph requires the number of teraoperations per second per Watt ($TOPS/W$), (4.4) is used. The unit $TOPS/W$ equals to teraoperations per joule (TO/J).

$$n_{eff} = \frac{n_{TO} * n_{inf}}{t_{took} * P_{mean}} \quad (4.4)$$

with:

- n_{eff} = energy efficiency in $TOPS/W = TO/J$
- n_{TO} = number of teraoperations of a model
- n_{inf} = number of inferences executed (here: 32)
- t_{took} = duration from the end of the warm up till the end of the last inference
- P_{mean} = mean power during t_{took}

To get the number of operations for each model, the model analyzer included in OpenVINO™ was used. This results in [Table 4.13](#).

Table 4.13: Number of Operations

MobileNetV1	0.001138 teraoperations
Inception V1	0.0030193 teraoperations

Fig. 4.24: Energy Efficiency MobileNetV1

Fig. 4.25: Energy Efficiency Inception V1

The first thing to notice is that the energy efficiency is about twice as high for Inception when comparing it to MobileNetV1. Up to a specific query size we can see an improvement in the energy efficiency. For the NCS2, the values stay rather constant with a samples per query size of ≥ 2 . Both Coral frequency modes behave quite similar, and its threshold query size is eight.

When comparing the results to Libutti *et al.* [10], we see that range of values is similar and the general trend of the graphs is the same. In the article, the NCS2 has relative constant behaviour too, even though this is also true for a query size of one. The energy efficiency of both frequency modes of Coral differ by around 1/4 of maximum frequency mode in the paper, whereas in the results here, there is no big discrepancy between the two models for a query size smaller than 16.

Accuracy

In the last part of this section, the accuracy of the inference is evaluated. The measurements from *Energy Efficiency* are used again here (samples-per-query = 1). Additionally, the accuracy is taken into account.

This time the AccuracyOnly Mode of MLPerf in combination with the whole dataset of 50000 samples is used.

Table 4.14: Measurement Parameters Accuracy

Measurement Setup	local
measured	accuracy
MLPerf Settings	
TestMode	AccuracyOnly
TestScenario	SingleStream
count	50000 (whole dataset)

Fig. 4.26: Accuracy in Relation to Performance

Fig. 4.27: Accuracy in Relation to Energy Efficiency

MobileNetV1 shows better accuracy for both accelerators, but lower TOPS and TOPS/W compared to Inception V1. When comparing to Fig. 6 in Libutti *et al.* [10], this behaviour can also be identified. The overall TOPS are much lower here than in the article. As for the reason, only speculation can be made, as to how the measurement and calculations were made is not disclosed in the article. Another thing to notice is the low accuracy for Inception V1 on NCS2. This is probably due to a slightly different model or preprocessing used here.

4.2.3 Power vs. Accuracy vs. Latency

Fig. 4.28: Comparison of Accuracy, Latency and average Power

Fig. 4.28 presents a comparison between accuracy, power and latency for each hardware and model. For this graph, the measurement with samples-per-query = 32 is used. The latency is the duration from the end of the warm-up till the end of the last inference divided by the number of inferences t_{took}/n_{inf} . The power is the average power consumption in the same time frame P_{mean} . One thing to notice is the similar values for Coral with MobileNetV1. When looking at the power profile a greater time duration from warm up till the first inference can be recognized for maximum frequency, possibly due to a longer loading time. This resulted in greater overall latency and lower average power and then in similar values, even though the inference parameters itself are different.

4.2.4 Layer Analysis

In order to be able to make solid predictions on the energy consumption of an accelerator during inference, a closer look is taken on the energy consumption of each individual layer of a model.

This is done in Wess *et al.* [16], again with NCS2 and Coral. In this paper, the models Tiny YOLOv3, YOLOv3 and MobileNetV2 are used.

This section of the thesis presents a part of this paper, to which I contributed to. I converted the models to be compatible with Coral as well as prepared the measurements for this accelerator. The data processing was not done by me and is taken from the paper. Here, only MobileNetV2 is looked at.

Coral provides no API in order to get the layer latency from the accelerator itself. The technique that was used, is to only execute a part of the model and to calculate the differences in run time. The preparation of the model was done during the compilation process for Coral by means of the Edge TPU Compiler as mentioned in [Model](#).

The measurement was performed with the NUC setup and no MLPerf Code was applied. As an input, dummy data was used instead of an actual dataset.

[Fig. 4.29](#) shows the inference power profile with the calculated layer transitions.

Fig. 4.29: Inference of MobileNetV2 on Coral std-f with layer transitions

Now the mean power and energy are compared to the run time of the respective layer. The results are shown in [Fig. 4.30](#) and [Fig. 4.31](#). The mean power for all layers is between $1.2 - 2W$. A layer execution can take up to $0.3ms$. The gray line represents the base power consumption of Coral of $1W$. Convolution, especially Depthwise Convolution layers seem to take the longest to execute and therefore consume the most energy. Some layers are concentrated around $1.8W$, where others average at around $1.4W$.

Fig. 4.30: Mean Power for each layer of MobileNetV2 on Coral std-f over the layer runtime

Fig. 4.31: Total Energy for each layer of MobileNetV2 on Coral std-f over the layer runtime

For further results see [16].

Chapter 5

Discussion

This chapter recaps the most important points of the thesis and discusses them. A benchmark execution consists of several parts. In the following we tried to come up with a simple energy estimation model. During the reproduction of Libutti *et al.* [10], we discovered that the inference duration becomes smaller with larger query size, whereas the power stays constant. Additionally, we noticed a greater idle time before the inference starts for greater query size.

5.1 MLPerf Inference Power Profile

For the task of power estimation, a mathematical model needs to be constructed. When looking at an inference power profile, it can be separated in four different sections with different power consumption:

- Idle
- Model loading
- Ready for inference
- Inference

The total energy then results in (5.1).

$$E_{tot} = E_{idle} + E_{load} + E_{stat} + E_{dyn} \quad (5.1)$$

with:

- E_{tot} = total energy
- E_{idle} = idle energy consumption
- E_{load} = energy used to load the model
- E_{stat} = energy used when model is loaded and ready for inference
- E_{dyn} = energy consumed additionally during inference

The idle energy can be written as $E_{idle} = P_{idle} * t_{idle}$. The idle power P_{idle} is only dependent on the hardware and therefore is a characterization parameter. t_{idle} is the idle time, it depends on the specific application.

In real-life applications the model loading process most likely only plays a minor role, cause it is executed rarely.

The inference power is 3 times (NCS2) and 4.6-5.8 times (Coral) larger when comparing to idle. After the model is loaded a lot of inferences will be executed in typical applications. Therefore, the specific energy consumption during inference represents a big part of the overall power consumption. When using MultiStream Mode of MLPerf the time duration of the end of the warmup till the first inference started was different for different query sizes. A reason for this could be loading times. Even though average power for different layers vary quite a bit, duration is a greater factor for energy consumption.

5.2 Recreate Measurements

All models were used with a fixed batch size of one. This means that all inferences were executed in serial order.

5.2.1 Latency and MLPerf Overhead

Here, we look at Fig. 3 and Fig. 7 of Libutti *et al.* [10].

As opposed to the article, the latency reported by MLPerf rises with increasing samples-per-query (Fig. 4.11, Fig. 4.12). This is due to the fact that the latency is measured for each sample from the start of the query till its execution is finished and all these latencies are then averaged. Mathematically, the duration of a single inference can be calculated. When drawing this values over the samples-per-query (Fig. 4.15, Fig. 4.17, Fig. 4.19), we get similar results to the one in Fig. 3 of [10].

To me that raises the question as to why the duration of an inference falls with rising samples-per-query anyway. Even the software timer shows this behaviour. Unfortunately, I can not think of any reason for this.

A minor thing that I noticed was, that in Fig. 7 of Libutti *et al.* [10], the data for Inception looks like it used Coral standard frequency, even though it says that maximum frequency mode is used.

5.2.2 Power and Energy Consumption

Now, we look at Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 of Libutti *et al.* [10].

The paper stated that the measurements are obtained at “inference engine invocation of MLPerf”. Here, the inferences were isolated out of the whole power profile to calculate the power values as opposed to taking the entire profile and taking the average from it. The power data then is not dependent on the samples-per-query. In Libutti *et al.* [10], this is not the case. The reason for this is the lower sampling rate as well as the fact that the whole inference process including idle time was measured (the gap between two queries is 50ms).

5.2.3 Accuracy

Finally, Fig. 6 of Libutti *et al.* [10] is discussed.

Why are results of Fig. 4.26 and Fig. 4.27 different to the one in Fig. 6 in the [10]? One reason for the accuracy difference could be that not the exact same models and preprocessing methods were used. The value TOPS/W depends on the model and the exact method of the measurement, therefore a lot of possible divergences are possible.

5.2.4 Additional Remarks

To restate what was already said in *Recreate Measurements*, the exact methods and what values are measured exactly are not explained in the article. This made it hard to reproduce the measurement results.

While in Libutti *et al.* [10] the voltage across the accelerator is measured, it is assumed to be fixed at 5V in this thesis. On page 8 of [10], the calculations for power are shown. Unfortunately, I can't follow the formula for the *loadvoltage*. The following is used: $loadvoltage = busvoltage + (shuntvoltage/1000)$. As stated in the paper, both *busvoltage* and *shuntvoltage* are given in *mV*. Both values are obtained via measurement with INA219. To me, the formulas only makes sense if *busvoltage* is given in *V*. *loadvoltage* is then used to calculate the power. I do not understand that, because *busvoltage* already is the voltage drop across the load [7]. With the presented calculation, *loadvoltage* therefore is the voltage provided by the USB port to my understanding (even though the variable names don't make a lot of sense then). For the fact that we only want the power of the load, I would directly use the measured *busvoltage* to calculate the power.

A completely other question would be, if the MultiStream Mode is necessary to gather insights or you can just use the lesser complex SingleStream Mode, which sends one sample after the other. There is still the unsolved question as to why the inference duration is lower for greater query size, therefore an answer if the use of MultiStream Mode makes sense, can not be given. If MultiStream Mode is not used, the question can also be posed if the use of MLPerf makes sense. Even though its already existing codebase and components as well as the detailed output it generates are helpful, it adds a lot of complexity to the measurement process. The input parameters are not explained in detail, so a lot of code examination and testing needed to be done to understand what they achieve. This is also true for the output, as for some variables different names are used in different files and their exact meaning is not documented very well.

In this thesis, the NCS2 was only used in synchronous mode. To improve performance, asynchronous mode provides the option to perform a number of so called inference requests in parallel.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

In this chapter the findings are summarized and an outlook at future work based on this thesis is presented.

6.1 Summary

When designing an estimator for a specific problem, it is first necessary to characterize the setup. This is done in this thesis for machine learning accelerators by looking at their power profile. The different hardware platforms lead to quite different results, whereas for another model the values doesn't deviate by the same degree here. With the presented setup, the measurements could easily be retaken for other USB hardware devices and models. This thesis also provides a good overview of the magnitudes of characteristic values, which is useful to get a sense for which factors have the greatest influence on inference parameters. We investigated and analyzed different combinations of measurement setups, hardware (modes), models and MLPerf parameters like LoadGen Scenario and query sizes.

6.2 Future Work

In a next step a mathematical model can then be created to estimate energy consumption. An approach would be to start with a simple model, e.g. just to multiply the number of inferences with average power draw and compare these results to a real measurement. If the prediction is not accurate enough, the model can be made more specific by considering idle time or power consumption of different layers for example. Due to time constraints this could not be evaluated further here. In addition to a characterization for model and hardware, the specific application plays a big role in overall energy usage and therefore could be specified and characterized as well.

One issue when measuring a power profile was, that there is currently no possibility to synchronize the power profile to the timestamps gathered. This had to be done by hand here, but could be solved by introducing a trigger impulse.

To make inference on the NCS2 more efficient, asynchronous mode with more than one inference request could be applied and investigated.

In the middle of 2021, power measurement rules were specified by MLPerf. These could also be taken into consideration.

Appendix A

USB 3 Current Sense Amplifier

Fig. A.1: USB 3 Current Sense Amplifier Render front

Fig. A.2: USB 3 Current Sense Amplifier Render back

Fig. A.3: USB 3 Current Sense Amplifier Layout front

Fig. A.4: USB 3 Current Sense Amplifier Layout back

Sheet: /
 File: usb_power_measurement.sch
Title: USB 3 Current Sense Amp
 Size: A4 | Date: 2022-01-13
 KiCad E.D.A. kicad (5.1.10)-1

Rev: 1.0
 Id: 1/1

Appendix B

Declaration of Authorship

Hiermit erkläre ich, dass die vorliegende Arbeit gemäß dem Code of Conduct – Regeln zur Sicherung guter wissenschaftlicher Praxis (in der aktuellen Fassung des jeweiligen Mitteilungsblattes der TU Wien), insbesondere ohne unzulässige Hilfe Dritter und ohne Benutzung anderer als der angegebenen Hilfsmittel, angefertigt wurde. Die aus anderen Quellen direkt oder indirekt übernommenen Daten und Konzepte sind unter Angabe der Quelle gekennzeichnet. Die Arbeit wurde bisher weder im In- noch im Ausland in gleicher oder in ähnlicher Form in anderen Prüfungsverfahren vorgelegt.

Vienna, Austria, 21.02.2022

Nikolas Alge

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